

Intercultural relations and problems of perception of their ethnic group among young people in a society in transition

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In the study of intercultural relations, it is important to take into account and understand the socio-cultural context in society, the tolerance of the ethnic majority and minority, the features of the integration of the group's past (collective memory), present and future in the ideas of young people. *The aim of our study* was to study the perception of their group by young people in a society in transition. The chosen sample was composed of Moldovan students (19–25). The total sample was of 200 respondents. The research period was in 2019. In order to study the perception of their group in the time perspective, the following questions were included in the research: “What qualities are characteristic of Moldovans?”; “What qualities are not typical of Moldovans?”; a projective question: “Who are the Moldovans: yesterday, today, tomorrow?”.

Results: 1. The following groups were identified: Moldovan youth, who clearly differentiate the characteristic and uncharacteristic qualities of a representative of their group; a group that highlights only the characteristic qualities of its group; a group that is undecided about the answer. The significant qualities for young people in the image of Moldovans are hospitality, hard work, ingenuity, sincerity. 2. The study of the peculiarities of the perception of their group in the time perspective among the Moldovan youth revealed a great variability: from “optimists”, who accounted for 43%, to “pessimists”, 29%. The common thing for the youth of Moldovans of all the selected groups is that in the past of their group, they positively assess its cultural heritage (traditions, customs, language, etc.). It seems that cultural heritage is a powerful resource for the preservation and development of positive ethnic identity and the optimization of intercultural relations.